

PREDICTION OF PROCESS-INDUCED DEFORMATIONS USING DEEP LEARNING INTERFACED FINITE ELEMENT CONSTITUTIVE MODELS

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Abstract:
The aim of the study is to improve the predictive capacity of a Finite Element (FE) tool in relation to a rheological thermo-chemo-viscoelastic constitutive model. This enhancement specifically focuses on accurately capturing the Process Induced Deformations (PID) resulting from the polymerization of the thermoset matrix. These deformations are due to the internal residual stress that arises from the material's inherent anisotropic properties, specifically the coefficients of thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage. The focus of the study is to accurately model the cure polymerization behaviour, which is known to have a significant impact on manufacturing defects. To account for the effect of process variables, such as maximum curing temperatures and temperature rates, a non-parametric neural network model is implemented instead of a parametric diffusion cure-kinetics model.

Process induced deformation in thermoset parts

Parameters influencing the PIDs in thermoset parts

Intrinsic parameters	Extrinsic parameters
Thermal conductivity	Mould
Mechanical properties	Friction properties
Coefficient of thermal expansion	Degree of vacuum
Coefficient of chemical shrinkage	Heating rates
Thickness	Cooling rates
Ply stacking sequence	Isothermal temperature dwells
Fibre volume fraction	Resin/fibre rich regions
Heat of reaction	

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) characterization tests :

DSC tests (rates of 1.5°C/min, 0.55°C/min, and 0.5°C/min & with isothermal dwells at 180°C, 175°C, and 185°C, respectively + some with partial curing) show that rates and dwells have an influence on the final state of the matrix. This raises the question of the interest for more representative kinetics models.

A new model should however ensure better general prediction and allow adapting to different resin formulations and variants.

Parametric diffusion cure-kinetics (Cole, et al. [1991]) and DiBenedetto's model (Stutz, et al. [1990])

The cure kinetics model is implemented to describe the development of cure in terms of polymerization rate, as given by:

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = \frac{K X^m (1-X)^n}{1 + e^C(X-X_c)}$$

where, $K = Ae^{-\Delta E/RT}$ and $X_c = t_0 - (t_1 T)$

K is the rate constant, R is the molar gas constant, A is the exponential law coefficient, E is the activation energy, m and n are the first and second exponential constants, C is the diffusion constant, t_0 is the critical X at the initial time and t_1 is a constant accounting for the increase in X with temperature, T . T_g is defined as a function of X . The generic function used is the DiBenedetto's relationship, which is given by,

$$\frac{T_g - T_{g0}}{T_{g\infty} - T_{g0}} = \frac{\lambda X}{1 - (1-\lambda)X}$$

T_{g0} and $T_{g\infty}$ are the glass transition temperature at the gel point and vitrification point respectively, and λ is the material dependent parameter when fitting equation to experimental measurements.

Drawbacks:

- No dependency on process condition variables.
- The part follows different temperature profiles than those used for fitting
- The model parameters are treated deterministically.

Non-parametric neural network model

The network characteristics are derived by employing a training algorithm that utilizes a gradient descent approach to minimize the error between the network's predictions and the expected outputs. The optimized network structure is represented as 3-13-13-2, with sigmoid activation functions in the hidden layers and a linear activation function in the output layer.

Comparison of performance to predict the evolution of reaction rate, $\frac{dX}{dt}$ for the case of $r = 1$ °C/min, with isothermal dwell at 180 °C

Residual stress prediction (Svanberg, et al. [2004])

The thermo-viscoelasticity for anisotropic and thermo-chemo-rheological materials is written in integral form as a function of instantaneous relaxation modulus,

$$\sigma(t) = C\epsilon + \int_0^t \delta C(\psi - \psi') \frac{\partial(\epsilon - \epsilon^E)}{\partial \tau} d\tau$$

$$C = C_\infty + \sum_{n=1}^N C_n e^{(-t)\rho^n} \forall X \geq X_{gel} \text{ else } C = 0$$

ψ and ψ' are the reduced time corresponding to spring and dashpot dependent on the curing state variables respectively and is defined as,

$$\psi = \int_0^t \frac{1}{a_T} dt'; \psi' = \int_0^t \frac{1}{a_T} dt'$$

The term a_T corresponds to shift factor in the constitutive model and is assumed to be taken as a function approaching 0 and infinity in rubbery and glassy state, respectively.

Full-scale model

Temperature & pressure profiles

PID prediction (spring-in angle measure) comparisons between different models

Summary: The study offers insights into the influence of process conditions on the evolution of cure state parameters. The non-parametric model is integrated with the viscoelastic constitutive model to make precise PID predictions. This modelling approach proves particularly useful when dealing with thick thermosets experiencing varying temperature gradients between the control temperature and the part temperature. The approach provides an accurate initial estimation of defects and facilitates the optimization of temperature profiles to reduce risks and enhance manufacturing quality.

Outlooks: The model could prove to be vital for characterizing complex resin formulations for newer thermoset materials without relying on Arrhenius formulations. Moreover, the model could be interfaced to conduct stochastic simulations, allowing for the quantification of uncertainties associated with cure temperature cycles.

